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Image [modified]: Ephemera, n. 5, April 1978 (Detail). Courtesy of Private Collection, Archivo La Fuente.

Latin American art in diaspora: migration and alternative networks of art in Europe in the 1960s and 1970s

Arte latino-americana na diáspora: migração e redes artísticas alternativas na Europa nas décadas de 1960 e 1970

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ABSTRACT

The article examines a network of artists from Latin America in Europe connected by their experience of exile and the set of transnational relations they created through their practices. It focuses on the Netherlands, and Amsterdam in particular, as a critical node and geo-artistic site in a broader diaspora of Latin American artists in Europe as of the 1960s. The essay centers on the work of Raul Marroquin (Colombia), Ulises Carrión (Mexico), Claudio Goulart and Flavio Pons (Brazil) and their production of publications and mail art that formed a significant artistic network in the postwar period. It examines how their work was key in establishing mediums of communication, connection and support among Latin American artists in Europe, as well as a larger international network of artists. In the widespread use of the term marginal and alternative to describe their unconventional art practices, this paper also considers a more capacious understanding of this vocabulary as it relates to these artists' peripheral position(s) and non-normative identities.

KEYWORDS

Latin America. Exile. Mail Art. Raúl Marroquín. Ulises Carrión. Claudio Goulart. Flavio Pons.

RESUMO

Este artigo examina uma rede de artistas da América Latina na Europa conectados por sua experiência de exílio, bem como o conjunto de relações transnacionais que eles criaram por meio de suas práticas. Ele se concentra na Holanda, em Amsterdã em particular, como um nó crítico e um local geoartístico em uma diáspora mais ampla de artistas latino-americanos na Europa a partir da década de 1960. O texto se concentra no trabalho de Raul Marroquin (Colômbia), Ulises Carrión (México), Claudio Goulart e Flavio Pons (Brasil) e em sua produção de publicações e mail art que formaram uma significativa rede artística no período pós-guerra. Ele examina como seu trabalho foi

fundamental para estabelecer meios de comunicação, conexão e apoio entre artistas latino-americanos na Europa, bem como criar uma maior rede internacional de artistas. No uso generalizado do termo marginal e alternativo para descrever suas práticas artísticas não convencionais, este artigo também visa uma compreensão mais ampla desse vocabulário, já que ele se relaciona com a(s) posição(ões) periférica(s) e identidades não normativas desses artistas.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE

América Latina. Exílio. Mail Art. Raul Marroquin. Ulises Carrión. Claudio Goulart. Flavio Pons.

In recent scholarship on Latin American art, a number of studies have focused their attention on expatriate artists or what Dária Jaremtchuk refers to as “artistic exiles” who were based in the United States, and primarily in New York, during the 1960s and 70s (Jaremtchuk, 2023; Lukin, 2022). New York figured as an attractive destination for a large number of Latin American artists who were motivated to flee violent dictatorial regimes back home, but also take advantage of opportunities to study abroad, develop cosmopolitan artistic profiles and potentially achieve international recognition. At the same time there was a notable segment of artists from different parts within Latin America that opted to go to Europe, and not specifically Paris, but rather cities in Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, East Germany and the United Kingdom. The reasons for their displacement was equally varied, but mirrors those of New York-based artists. Despite their dispersed locations in Europe, they were connected vis-à-vis an international, experimental artistic network that produced and circulated mail art and DIY publications, which catalyzed a complex and largely under-explored transnational community of “artistic exiles”.

For the purposes of this essay, I will focus on one critical node in this networked configuration – the Netherlands, in the North Eastern part of Europe, which attracted several Latin American artists: Raul Marroquin and Miguel Ángel Cardénas from Colombia, Ulises Carrión from Mexico, Claudio Goulart and Flavio Pons from Brazil. What is perhaps unique about these migrant artists is that each of them permanently stayed in the Netherlands. In what follows, I explore these artists’ stories of migration, their formation of a diasporic artistic community of Latin American artists and transnational artistic scene that made “marginal” art that took the form of artistic-run spaces, publications, mail art, performance and video art. The essay focuses on two publications in particular, *Ephemera* and *Fandangos* as a means of communication and connection to Latin American artists within Europe and internationally. I analyze the experimental and collaborative aspects of this work to demonstrate the ways in which it was a critical medium of communication and connection in the diaspora of Latin American artistic exiles in Europe, and for a broader international network of artists. I contend that these works were key in co-creating alternative artistic spaces for marginal artists and practices. Furthermore, they were predicated on new transnational relationships and mobile mail art objects that reshaped the scope of internationalism in art from the 1970s. Finally, I interrogate artists use of the terms “marginal” or “alternative” to describe their art practices in relation to “the center”. This vocabulary referenced an experimental and transgressive model of art based on working outside institutional structures and the art market, diverse practices and challenges to conventional ideas about artistic authorship or production. This essay, however, considers a more capacious understanding of artists’ “marginal” posturing, one which takes their alterity to be a significant conceptual framework that marks their relationship to a number of imagined centers: artistic, national, cultural, sexual. But rather than assume these artists affirmed a peripheral position, I argue that their marginal art was a counter-hegemonic practice that pushed against multiple dominant systems.

I suggest that such a history accomplishes several things: it challenges binaries like center and periphery, complicates the stability of national and regional signifiers such as “Latin American art” and presents us with different geographic and spatial imaginaries within histories of art. This topic more broadly speaks to the changing study of art that maps the transnational, cross-geographic flows of art that characterize the global world, and the importance of art in redrawing conventional borders in the globalized present. It is in dialogue with Diana Sorensen’s noted shift in perspective that has “the world [being] remapped along differing principles of organization” and “regimes of representation” as scholars turn their attention to mobility and migration (Sorensen, 2018: 14). It also aligns with Burcu Dogramaci’s work that foregrounds a migratory turn in art history whereby transnational histories based on “migration, exile, flight” necessitate new forms of mapping and models (Dogramaci, 2020: 10). The present essay is one approach to writing an art history of migration that addresses overlooked practices of Latin American exiles in Europe and their collaborative production, which in turn establishes a wider and less familiar set of coordinates from this period.

Amsterdam

The Netherlands was not the initial destination for the majority of Latin American artists who migrated there. With the exception of Raul Marroquín, who left Colombia in 1971 on a fellowship to complete a Masters in Graphic Arts at the Jan Van Eyck Academy in Maastricht, the artists Cardénas, Carrión, Goulart and Pons first received grants to study art in Spain and literature in France. Their eventual move to the Netherlands between 1962 and 1976 was prompted by a set of perceived favorable conditions. When asked why he arrived to the Netherlands, Miguel Ángel Cardénas recounts,

In Barcelona, I made a very good Spanish friend who was also in the art school studying Graphic arts. He spoke to me about his friend in the Hague that had a gallery. In addition, he told me that in Holland there was a lot of tolerance of homosexuals. The so-called ‘gallery’ was an antique store that did not interest me and the owner thought my work was scandalous and immoral. But a week later I met [curator] Wim Beerens and I invited him to see my artworks” (Cárdenas, 2010: 211, my translation).

Cárdenas’ anecdote speaks to how both art and sexuality shaped his migratory experience and orientation towards the Netherlands. In his 1981 video work *Somos Libres?!*, the artist reveals more to his story through the narration of two gay men who flee a place characterized by violent oppression in the form of physical torture executed by representations of the church, a militarized state and bougeois class, to eventually arrive to the Netherlands. Moments of celebration and exclamations of “somos libres” are quickly diminished by modes of exclusion in response to their presumed gay coupling and drag appearance¹ [Fig 1-2].

FIGS. 1-2. Miguel Ángel Cárdenas, Film stills from *Somos Libres*, 1981. Courtesy of LI-MA.

While Cárdenas’ illuminates the persistent marginality that he experienced as a gay man in the Netherlands, what is clear is that his sexuality was central to his displacement from Colombia to a place imagined

as more liberal and free. Furthermore his video work reveals the different forms and experiences of violent oppression in Latin America, which played a role in a number of artists' exile.

Since the 1950s, Amsterdam in particular had an international reputation for being a "gay capital", which was attributed to a convergence of factors, including a growing number of exclusive, safe spaces for the gay community, the rising visibility of gay public figures and an influential homophilia movement (Hekma, 1999)². With the onset of the sexual revolution in the 1960s in the Netherlands came the abolition of religious, criminal and psychiatric discrimination of homosexuality and the achievement of certain, but still very limited, gay rights, which however advanced the perception that Amsterdam was a site of queer liberation.

In the case of Ulises Carrión, he left Mexico in 1965 to first study at the Sorbonne in Paris and then complete a master's degrees in English Literature at the University of Leeds before moving to Amsterdam in 1970, where he stayed until the end of his life. His personal writings reveal the multiple motivations behind his migratory movement. In a Dutch newspaper article written by Carrión, titled, "Ik ben een geboren buitenlander" (I am a native foreigner), the artist explained how at the early age of 5 years old he would ask his parents to give him away to other families, neighbors or relatives as an early indication of his desire to move away. He writes, "I knew from a young age that I would go on the road. In the beginning to me that just meant 'away from this city' - my birthplace. And later, when I learned the concept of nationality 'away from this country' - Mexico" (Carrión, 1983)³. What can be read from Carrión's text is a broader sense of estrangement, from both family and nation. In Heriberto Yépez's reading of Ulises Carrión's transition from a writer of traditional Mexican literature to an experimental transnational artist, he concludes that Carrión actively developed a post-national identity - a deliberate break from a culturally oppressive "macho literary world" (Yepez, 2016: 19). A key figure in this world was poet Octavio

Paz whose 1950 book *The Labyrinth of Solitude* demonstrates how Mexican national and cultural identity were imbricated with sexuality. Important for this discussion is the way Paz's book defines the character of male *mexicanidad* in terms of virile masculinity and homosexuality as inferior, passive, abject and degraded. As Edward J. McCaughan notes, male Mexican identity was utterly incompatible with homosexuality, which I suspect played a role in Carrión's sense of marginalization (McCaughan, 2012: 61). Similar to Cardénas' story of migration, Carrión sought a new destination and more fitting location that was beyond the framework of a dominant and oppressive heterosexism.

Brazilian artist Flavio Pons was already established in Amsterdam in 1976 when Claudio Goulart visited him. Goulart, who was in Barcelona pursuing his artistic studies, saw the opportunity to develop his work within the Netherlands' experimental art scene, but also deepen his relationship with Pons who became his partner in art and life. In a letter written by Goulart to Carrión in 1979, he describes Porto Alegre as provincial and dominated by "commercial and reactionary" art spaces, while Brazil remained under tense social and political conditions (Goulart, Ulises Carrión Collection, 1979)⁴. His diagnosis of Brazil suggests that, like his contemporaries, Goulart sought alternatives to Porto Alegre's limited and conventional art scene.

In addition to the relative freedoms they might have found in the Netherlands, the Dutch government afforded prolonged stays to immigrant artists and financial subsidy systems to national and foreign artists, like the Beeldende Kunstenaars Regeling (Visual Artists Program) that abetted their artistic activity (Delhaye, 2008; Wasielewski, 2019). Once in Amsterdam, artists Cardenas, Carrión, Goulart and Pons coalesced around their artistic practices and likely, queer affiliation. In 1972, Cardenas, Carrión and Marroquín co-founded the independent artist-run space In-Out Center in a canal house in the center of Amsterdam with six other artists as a space for "actions, objects, films and publications"⁵. I argue that

it served as a laboratory in which many of these artists developed new experimental practices, processes of networked affiliations and modes of artistic interaction (Mazadiego, 2022). It was a catalyst for the formation of an alternative, or sometimes called “marginal” model of art based in the Netherlands, but globally connected. Its premise was to work outside institutional structures and the art market through a system of artistic autonomy. Art historian and friend to Cardenas, Tineke Reijnders recalls that the artist, “felt an urgency to establish an independent space on a democratic, non-profit, experimental basis, focusing on young and good art” (Reijnders, 2017: n.p.). Even though In-Out Center would close in 1974, this ethos would endure in the artists’ later work. This is evidenced in Marroquín and Carrión’s mail art production and publications, as well as Carrión’s establishment of a new space Other Books and So (OBAS). In these projects, Carrión and Marroquin produced artwork with Claudio Goulart and Pons, while Goulart and Pons produced a series of performances and video work together.

Already during In-Out Center’s tenure, Carrión was using the space to generate opportunities to work with Latin American artists based in other parts of Europe, notably Felipe Ehrenberg and Martha Hellion – Mexican artists based in Devon who had established the independent publishing venue Beau Geste Press (BGP) with David Mayor. In 1973, Carrión used his role as the space’s co-organizer and co-curator to invite Ehrenberg and Hellion exhibit their work at In-Out Center, which resulted in the show *Condition (String Event)*. The later artistic projects that I will detail further, such as the DIY publications *Fandangos*, led by Marroquin, and Carrión’s *Ephemera* were important in establishing other platforms through which they could connect, communicate and collaborate with what I refer to as a Latin American diaspora in Europe, and more broadly an international network of marginal artists. Amsterdam was therefore significant both for its relative concentration of Latin American artists in comparison to other parts of Europe, which I’ve argued is related to the city’s perceived liberal

attitudes and support of artists, and for the kind of spaces (physical and conceptual) that these artists established for their networked activities, which made the city such a critical node in the web of relations among Latin American artists in the diaspora.

In comparison to London, which attracted a remarkable number of Latin American artists as of the mid-1960s, the activities of its artistic exiles were largely decentralized and not particularly committed to developing connections amongst each other or with the diaspora of artists in Europe⁶. The exceptions were Ehrenberg and Hellion who were first in London before establishing themselves in Devon and created the magazine *Documento Trimestral* in 1971 as a point of contact among Latin American artists in England. As Carmen Juliá describes, the publication was Ehrenberg's early endeavor during his self-exile to develop a network built on exchange and distribution (Juliá, 2018).

Artistic publications and networked communities

The short-run publication *Ephemera* was first launched in November 1977 by Ulises Carrión, Aart von Barneveld and Salvador Flores. In its pages are a collection of works received through the mail. Artists dispersed across the world, but representative of the editors' social circle, sent their creations to Carrión's artist-run space OBAS in Amsterdam. From there, the individual works were pasted into a collage and reproduced in a simple broadsheet format using a mimeo press. The editors describe the publication as a "monthly journal of mail and ephemeral art" [Fig. 3]. On the front page of the first issue, five mail artworks are featured with a handwritten caption indicating the artist's name, the work's title, a date and the location from which it was sent. One contribution from Judtih Hoffman in Los Angeles is the typescript "Art Spoken Here", which echoes the predominant linguistic

quality of mail art and the works contained in this publication. Elsewhere on the page is a stamp placed just above the journal's title, which references the postal system by which the mail art world relies on for circulation and distribution. Another image from the inside pages shows the participation of Harry Ruhé, a Fluxus artist from Amsterdam, and Ivald Granato, a multimedia artist from Sao Paulo. Granato's text titled "The Artist in Search of a Profession" proposed to send you an original from the artist's production in exchange for 20USD. The first line reads "This work doesn't have the aim of explaining or creating a new cultural elite; it just proposes a reality of thought that many change the vehiculation of the art's market." It summarizes the general ethos of the editors and artists involved in this publication, which was to operate outside of the institutional art system by controlling their processes of production and distribution.

FIG. 3. Front page of *Ephemera*, n. 1, November 1977. Courtesy of Private Collection, Archivo La Fuente.

FIG. 4. *Ephemera*, n. 5, April 1978. Courtesy of Private Collection, Archivo La Fuente.

In Issue number 5, an image of scissors and the question “Do you really want to look at this journal?” invites the reader in a form of somatic participation. At the same time, the front page also takes a serious tone with the large exclamation in the top right portion that reads: “Padin and Caraballo are in Jail! This is followed by Ulises Carrión’s small caption and remark to “Ask for information. Transmit It” [Fig.4]. The message refers to the arrest and disappearance of experimental artists Clemente Padin and Jorge Caraballo in 1977 under the repressive military regime in Uruguay. They were arrested for their mail art and visual poetry which openly criticized the Uruguayan dictatorship’s human rights violations. The news of Padin and Caraballo’s unlawful arrest and precarious situation was circulated through mail art circuits, such as we see here in *Ephemera*, with

the hopes of generating more attention. For Ulises Carrión, the publication was a critical information medium that reached an international readership. The last two issues thematized specific countries: Hungary and Brazil. Their contents served to showcase the culture of mail art practices in these local contexts outside the West, and the magazine's centrality in both facilitating and eventually archiving their cross-border artistic exchange.

Ephemera, as a collaborative artistic project produced by a diverse and geographically dispersed network of artists, constitutes an alternative artistic model Carrión aspired to create. In his text for his 1979 mail art exhibition *Artists' Postage Stamps and Cancellations Stamps*, published in the monthly bulletin *Rubber*, he reflects on his mail art projects as "an artist's attempt to organize in a coherent way, a chaotic range of ideas, feelings, experiences, objects, but also machines, distances, postal regulations, time uncertainties, and most strikingly, Mail-Art pieces from other artists" (Carrión, 1979, n.p.). From the same publication, his essay "Personal Worlds or Cultural Strategies" describes mail art as

shifting the focus from what is traditionally called 'art' to the wider concept of 'culture.' And this shift is what makes mail art truly contemporary. In opposition to 'personal worlds', mail art emphasizes cultural strategies. This radical shift gives birth to quite a number of theoretical and practical questions, the most evident of them being, where does the border lie between artist's work and the actual organization and distribution of the work (Carrión, 1979, n.p.; 1980, 51).

Mail art as a genre, defined by artists' use of the postal system to create and circulate small-scale artworks, came to prominence in the 1960s among artists experimenting with Fluxus and Conceptual art approaches. Carrión avoided either classification, tending to refer to his practice as "Language Art" or "Alternative art", which encompasses mail art, but also artist books, magazines, video and performance. In particular, he put emphasis on their experimental approach to art overall. While Carrión may not have

self-identified as a fluxus or conceptual artist, evidence of his dialogue with these groups is located in the pages of *Ephemera*. Moreover, his embrace of publishing as an inherent challenge to the unique object and market-driven artistic production, echoed the tenets of conceptual and fluxus practices. But Carrión and his peers also transcended their limits by resisting a western-centric geographical scope and an absorption into art markets.

As important to Carrión's mail art practice was the development of independent, alternative art spaces, such as In-Out Center and later Other Books and So. These independent, yet collaborative artistic modes of production and distribution point to the artists' motivations within the alternative art network that sought to challenge conventional ideas about artistic authorship, the unique art object, as well as circumvent commercial and institutional frameworks. The particular collaborative structure often involved his community of artistic exiles from Latin America, such as Raúl Marroquin, but also Felipe Ehrenberg and Martha Hellion located in Devon, England and Horacio Zabala in Rome, Italy. At the same time, Other Books and So and its projects became an important node within the larger mail art configuration. In 1977 OBAS exhibited Horacio Zabala's mail art project and book, titled *Art is a Prison*, which featured a large number of mail artists but also fluxus and conceptual artists based in Europe and Latin America [Fig 5]. The following year Carrión organized an exhibition of "books, postcards, mail-art projects, etc" by Zabala, Guillermo Deisler (from Chile, but living in the GDR), Edgardo Antonio Vigo (Argentina), Clemente Padin and Jorge Caraballo (Uruguay). In response to Padin and Caraballo's imprisonment, the exhibition was presented as a "homage (...) and as a protest against their incarceration." (Carrión, 1978: n.p). A letter to Carrión's mail art network described the context of the exhibition and request to sign a written declaration of protest that would be forwarded to the Ambassador of Uruguay in the Netherlands. Thanks to the international response to the artists' imprisonment, Clement Padin served a shortened prison sentence⁷. While politics filtered through Carrión's mail art project as seen through

these examples, and potentially made subtle political interventions, projects like *Ephemera* was among his many artistic strategies for engaging within the mail art network, but also facilitating its ongoing and necessary circulation.

FIG.5. *art is a Prison: Horacio Zabala's Project-Book*, 1977. Courtesy of Institute for the Studies on Latin American Art (ISLAA) Library and Archives.

Similar to *Ephemera* was the large-format silkscreen publication *Fandangos*, edited by Raúl Marroquin in collaboration with Theo van der Aa, Ger van Dijk and Marjo Schumans. Like *Ephemera*, the publication facilitated collaborations that were otherwise inhibited by physical distance. Its first issue, printed in December 1973, included reproductions of artworks by Ulises Carrión, but also featured contributions by Felipe Ehrenberg and Cecilia Vicuña – a Chilean artist based in the UK at the time [Fig 6]. Vicuña included the phrase “Chile is not, Chile is ELICH”, which is also found in

her artist book *Sabor A Mi*, published by Beau Geste Press in 1973. The word ELICH was a visual inversion of the word Chile, referring to the subversion of its democracy by the coup d'état and death of Salvador Allende in 1973. Juxtaposed with Vicuña's text was an announcement of Colombian artist Antonio Caro's work *El Imperialismo es un tigre de Papel* (Imperialism Is a Paper Tiger) at the Museum of Modern Art in Bogota⁸. The editors of *Fandangos* stated its aim to communicate "projects, documentation, ideas, commentaries and activities", echoing In-Out Center's original claims to "communicate ideas, works and problems". The textual references to Vicuña and Caro's work can be read as a line of communication about the political events unfolding in Latin America, as well as artistic events and work produced from this region. In their third issue, a photograph of Marroquin with Carrión, Ehrenberg and Hellion, under the heading BGP < Fandangos, function as a visual archive of the many collaborations and forms of reciprocity between Latin American artistic exiles in Europe⁹.

FIG. 6. *Fandangos*, Issue 1, December 1973. Courtesy of Corinne Groot and In-Out Center Archives.

Claudio Goulart's one-off bulletin *Daily Art*, featured in *Rubber* Vol. 4, number 1, gave the appearance of a mail art publication similar to *Ephemera* and *Fandangos*. The work replicated the newsprint page layout assemble of Goulart's stamp works, publicity for Carrión's Other Books and So and prompts to activate readers' participation and response. One stamp simply stating "space for art, C. Goulart" alludes to the publication's spatial dimension akin to Howardena Pindell's claim that artist periodicals could be conceived as alternative spaces (Pindell, 1977). Moreover, artist publications, according to art historians Gwen Allen and Zanna Gilbert, are quintessentially "counterpublic spheres" (Allen, 2011; Gilbert, 2019). They are alternative spaces in which artistic communities, especially those marginalized by mainstream institutions, might coalesce to develop their own artistic criteria and forms of expression. Indeed, the publications within this essay were the medium by which the editors created new artistic communities, predicated on an experimental approach that reconceptualized conventional notions of art, while privileging process, ideas, communication and systems. Furthermore, the mobility of mail art and the magazine was particularly important in transcending spatial limits and manifesting a particular mode of internationalism, based on distinct trajectories and transnational circulatory practices. In particular, these publications were modalities that formulated conceptual forms of sociality, community and kinship, fostered by collaborations and connections among a diasporic community of Latin American artists in Europe and a broader cross-geographic exchange with artists based in Latin America, Asia, Eastern Europe and Canada. In *Ephemera's* 9th issue the front cover page bears the title "poetry as social environment" referring to its collective character. Unique to this issue was an insert of the artist-run publication *Nervo Óptico* produced by the N.O. group based in Porto Alegre, into its center pages. The artists behind the Brazilian publication were similarly committed to an alternative model of art based on working outside institutional structures and the art market

through a system of artistic autonomy. This example, however, points to the ways artists across geographic distances worked together and supported each other's work through modes of presentation and circulation.

Marginal art

In 1974 Hervé Fischer published *Art et Communication Marginale* (*Art and Marginal Communication*) with the essay "Mass Media and Marginal Communications" which discusses "subcultures and their specific means of diffusion: the marginal media" (Fischer, 1974: 19). This publication is one of several texts by artists that define mail art and stamps as a marginal art practice or form of marginal communication. Zanna Gilbert's work on artist Eduardo Antonio Vigo gives evidence of his frequent use of the term "marginal" in relation to mail art. Like Fischer, Vigo viewed mail as marginal in the ways it operated outside of mass media circuits of communication, was structured as a two-way dialogic process of sending and receiving and facilitated distanced transmission. He wrote, "MAILART has produced the contact of international marginalities, the extension of their interchanges, the distribution of their multiples, the exchange or the polemics of their theories, inviting profound dialogue" (quoted in Gilbert, 2019; 249).

The term marginal was largely used to characterize the mode of communication, but also the artistic practice and posturing. As Fischer wrote in his publication, mail art emerged "out of necessity to invent [artists'] own means of communication, in order to assert their own existence" (Fischer, 1974: 19). As Fischer indicates, artists experimenting with mail art, but also working with DIY publications and establishing independent art spaces, were effectively marginalized from, as much as consciously marginal to the mainstream – from hegemonic systems of communication to art institutions and market.

The artists whom are the focus of this essay were actively involved in exhibitions framed as “marginal communications” or “marginal art”, from Guy Schraenen’s 1977 *Éditions and Communications marginales d’Amérique Latine* to the 1978 show *La Post/Avanguardia: Marginal Art and Marginality of Art*¹⁰. While the margin effectively references their experimental and transgressive models of art, these artists arguably were marginal to a number of dominant paradigms – national, cultural and sexual. Their transnational and non-normative subjectivities conceivably situated them within social and cultural margins. In other words, these artists occupied but also constructed a multiplicity of margins that were artistically and culturally generative. For the purposes of this paper, I leave the topic of margins open as a potentially useful concept that expands beyond their alternatives to conventional art practices to become a *loci* of contestation and refusal of static, dominant practices in art and life.

From the perspective of migration and mobility, the artists and their experimental artworks generated a transnational form of art situated in both the local and global, while transcending center and periphery divides. Through an examination of mail art and DIY publications, I illustrated the multi-faceted work they do – from producing contact zones between a diasporic network of Latin American artists in Europe to facilitating communication between Latin America and Europe and forming new international networks of collaboration in the 1970s. At the same time, the case of Carrión and his peers problematize the national and regional classifications art historians have relied on. Instead, artists from this group invite us to think transnationally or “plurinationally” (to use Ehrenberg’s language), and challenge us to remap their cultural flows.

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Notes

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- 1 I deal with this artwork in more depth in another forthcoming essay titled, "Somos Libres?!": alternative art networks and Latin American queer diasporas in Amsterdam".
- 2 Specifically, bars and discos, namely: DOK, Schakel, Hotel Tiemersma, Argos, LL, Motor Sportclub Amsterdam, however this changes by the late 1960s and 1970s to include other sorts of social spaces.
- 3 My translation with the support of DeepL. I am a native foreigner, newspaper article, Archivo LaFuente.
- 4 Goulart cites two exceptions the experimental Espaço N.O. (1979-1982) by Vera Chaves Barcellos and 542.
- 5 The additional co-founders of In-Out Center were Hetty Huisman, Peter L. Mol and G.J de Rook from

the Netherlands and Kristján Gudmunsson, Sigurdur Gudmundsson and Hreinn Fridfinnsson from Iceland.

- 6 Including Felipe Ehrenberg and Martha Hellion for a brief period, but also Cecilia Vicuña (Chile), Hélio Oiticica (Brazil), Leopoldo Maler and David Lamelas (Argentina), among others.
- 7 Geoffrey Cook describes how shortly after the mail art campaigns Caraballo was released from prison and paroled, while Padín was paroled later in 1979. While Cook doesn't fully attribute mail art to their release, he does suggest they may have played a role in influencing the Uruguayan government (Cook, 1984).
- 8 Caro's environmental work which was a large, red silk banner printed with a Spanish translation of Mao Zedong's statement was included in a group exhibition titled *New Names in Colombian Art*.
- 9 See *Fandangos* (Phandangos), Issue 3 (1974).
- 10 In an essay on Carrión, Guy Schraenen would describe the international circuit in which Carrión was dedicated to as marginal (Schraenen, 2016, 19).

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